

CODECO

Cognitive Decentralised
Edge Cloud Orchestration

D3: Data Management and Ethics Handling 2.0

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Executive Summary

D3 is a deliverable of WP1 which provides guidelines and an update on data management and ethics aspects concerning the work developed from month one to month 18 of the project. D3 is an intermediate report which covers the “*Data Management and Ethics Handling*”, a key element of good data management in Horizon Europe projects. As part of making research data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Re-usable (FAIR), ethical dimensions of handling the IoT data that is necessary for the use-cases, and how to correctly manage them throughout the project are considered.

This deliverable serves as the second version of the “*Data Management and Ethics Handling*”, updating the initial version regarding types of data and the received information, by project partners, on the data they have been generating under CODECO’s activities.

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Disclaimer

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List of Acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
3GPP	3 rd Generation Partnership Project
AAA	Authentication, Authorization, Accounting
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CA	Consortium Agreement
CC	Creative Commons
CDN	Content Delivery Network
CLI	Command Line Interface
CODECO	Cognitive, Decentralised Edge-Cloud Orchestration
CSV	Comma Separated Values
DL	Deep Learning
DME	Data Management and Ethics Handling
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EC	European Commission
ECL	Eclipse
EN	Edge Node
ETC	Ethics Committee
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Re-Usable
GeA	General Assembly
HE	Horizon Europe
IoT	Internet of Things
IP	Internet Protocol
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
K8s	Kubernetes
ML	Machine Learning
OSS	Operational Support Systems
PDF	Portable Data Format
PDLC	Privacy-preserving Decentralised Learning and Context-awareness
PII	Personally Identifiable Information
QoE	Quality of Experience
QoS	Quality of Service
UC	Use Case
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

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1 Introduction

CODECO Deliverable D3 - *Data Management and Ethics Handling (DME)* is a document detailing the management of all the data generated by the project, developed in the context of WP1, Task 1.1 – Project and Data Management. The aim of this deliverable is to provide data management guidelines following the Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable (FAIR) principles.

The DME establishes guidelines towards the handling of data, protection of personal, business, and confidential data. DME provides an initial overview on dataset formats in CODECO, and how such datasets will be provided to the consortium, and to the public. Instructions for storage, generation and deletion are also detailed.

The procedures established aim at opening as much as possible the generated datasets, based on open repositories, namely, the CODECO Zenodo community¹, the CODECO Website², and the Eclipse (ECL) CODECO research repository³. Datasets shall be identified by a *Digital Object Identifier (DOI)* and follow as much as possible open licensing.

CODECO is an orchestration framework that provides support for data management, decentralised data workflow, dynamic computation offloading, adaptive networking services, and privacy-preserving decentralized learning mechanisms. It includes open cognitive toolkits, a developer-oriented open-source software repository, training tools, use-cases across multiple domains, open calls, and community events, and an experimentation framework supporting large-scale experiments and integration into large-scale platforms such as EdgeNet⁴ for experimentation. In this context, the data related to the use-cases and project development, even more the collect IoT data is of extreme relevance to the DME.

As a research project, CODECO is concerned with proper and effective management of reach data, which is a very broad term that comprises different types of data. In this direction, the project adheres to best practices regarding:

- (i) The preparation of DME as a living document that will be regularly updated throughout the project's lifetime.
- (ii) The transfer and deposit of data in a trusted repository which will be openly accessible following the principle: "*as open as possible, as closed as necessary*".
- (iii) The provision of information about any research output and other tools that can be used to repurpose, reuse, and validate the data.

As part of making research data findable, accessible, interoperable, and re-usable (FAIR), the CODECO's DME handles the following aspects:

- What data will be collected per use-case, processed, and/or generated.
- The handling of research data during and after the end of the project.
- Which methodology will be applied.
- Whether data will be shared/made open access for verification and reuse and how.
- How data will be curated and preserved during and after the end of the project.
- How the data will preserve privacy and be secure throughout the project.

¹ <https://zenodo.org/communities/he-codeco/>

² <https://he-codeco.eu/>

³ <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project>

⁴ <https://www.edge-net.org/>

This revised and updated version of the DME includes the description of the information about the main datasets that will be produced and managed in the project. This collection was performed based on the template presented in Annex 1.

1.1 Document Structure

The deliverable comprises, in addition to this section, the following sections:

- **Section 2 – Data Summary** provides an overview on the types of data, data collection aspects, and data formats.
- **Section 3 – FAIR Data** describes the FAIR methodology applied in CODECO for data findability, interoperability, and handling.
- **Section 4 – Allocation of Resources** covers the responsibility of Partners regarding data management and curation.
- **Section 5 – Data Preservation, Storage, and Privacy** addresses the methodology for data storage, backup, and deletion.
- **Section 6 – Ethical Aspects** covers the ethical methodology and processes followed in CODECO.
- **Section 7 – Others** summarizes any other issue at the current DME version.
- **Section 8 – Use-cases Considerations** addresses data curation and management aspects for the CODECO use-cases.
- **Section 9 – Summary** concludes the deliverable.
- **Annex I** - provides the CODECO dataset template for data collection.
- **Annex II-Annex VII** – provide information on collected data sets until now.

1.2 Dependencies

D3 corresponds to the DME and covers data management and ethical aspects. Relevant deliverables that relate with D3 are:

- D1 – CODECO Handbook and Gender-Neutral Guidelines, M3 and revision in M12.
- D2 – Data Management and Ethics Handling, Version 1, M3.
- D5 and D6 Risk Assessment and Management Plan, M3 and M18.
- D21 – Dissemination, Communication, Promotion Plan, M3.

2 Data Summary

2.1 Types of Data

Different types of data will be collected, generated, and processed in the CODECO project which represent a starting point to be regularly revised in the project, as described next and summarized in Table 1.

- **Project Management and Coordination data:** data used internally in the management of the project, including minutes, project reports, financial and progress reports, data collected on the communication and dissemination events, as well as partners contact list and project deliverables (public and confidential).

- **Experimental data:** data concerning the use-case pilots, its processing and aggregation results on the edge and communication metadata.
- **Research data:** data used to develop the CODECO technologies such as surrogate datasets used to train *Machine Learning (ML)* algorithms.
- **Derived data:** data resulting from the processing and analysis of data collected in the project, both at the Edge-Cloud as well as processed data and curated databases with the partners.
- **Source code:** CODECO assets comprise, among others, open-source code that is publicly available via the following ECL GitLab research project⁵. This code is subject to review, updates, and overall source-code management rules. Although it is not considered directly “Data”, it is effectively the result of the work carried out in this project and needs to be placed here for consistency and discussed where deemed necessary.
- **Engagement data:** CODECO counts with a *Research and Innovation Community Engagement Programme - IRCEP (WP7)* and shall also interact with the open-source community.

Table 1: Categories of datasets expected in CODECO.

Data set	Examples	WP
Project management and coordination data	Project reports, GeA meeting minutes, financial and progress reports	WP1
Experimental data	Data from use-cases, from the Innovation and Community Engagement Programme	WP3-WP5, WP7
Research data	Data used for the development and validation of CODECO technologies	WP3-WP5`
Derived data	Scientific publications, white papers, presentations, videos	WP3-WP6
Source code	CODECO toolkits and components; CODECO Apps developed for use-cases	WP3-WP5
Outputs derived from AB meetings	Meeting minutes, surveys, etc.	WP1
Outputs from IRCEP	Surveys, polls, minutes, proceedings	WP7
Engagement data	Datasets derived from IRCEP and from additional cooperative and interaction meetings, e.g., minutes, proceedings	WP6, WP7

2.2 Data Collection

On a first level of the project, data collection includes mainly project management related data (meetings, work or visit plans, venues, and dates), architecture and frameworks documentation with versioning and traceability, meeting minutes and protocols with list of participants, and project reports / deliverables. Data will be, as far as possible, stored in widely used formats such as MS Excel (.xls/.xlsx, .csv), MS Word (.docx), image files (.jpeg, .TIFF), among others. Most files are expected to be small. CODECO does not rule out the use of datasets with richer semantics and metadata (e.g., labelled datasets) should this be required for research purposes. On the first level, data is collected to assist the internal operations in the project and therefore can be stored on the internal CODECO repository. When public, such data is stored in the CODECO Zenodo community⁶.

⁵ <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project>

⁶ <https://zenodo.org/communities/he-codeco/>

Data collected at a second level of the project, corresponds to source code development. This data (OSS code) is being collected, updated, and documented via the CODECO Eclipse Gitlab Research project⁷.

In the third level of the project, data is expected to be collected from different cyber physical systems for instance due to input to use-cases (e.g., sensors, energy systems) and will be organized in datasets per use-case. This corresponds to the creation of raw data (semi-processed data from, e.g., sensors, cameras). This data can be useful to the scientific community upon request or assessment; for industries eventually to analyse its suitability to their context. This data needs to be processed for removal of directly and indirectly identifying *personally identifiable information (PII)* before storage. This data is therefore handled in CODECO via WP1, and curated by a specific team, foregoing also the proposed ethical processes (rf. to section 5, 6). If public, the data will be stored on the CODECO Eclipse Gitlab Research project.

In the fourth level, derived data from the collected experimental data will be created. This refers to scientific and analytical analysis resulting from the execution of the source code (second level on top of the collected cyber-physical system data (third level)). This will be relevant to scientific community as well as for use by the public, for example, when publishing news on the social media/website, or on data observatories. Such data is collected via deliverables and reports as well as via scientific publications, which are stored in the CODECO Zenodo community.

2.3 Data Formats

Formats proposed to assist in aligning the work developed and the data curation are described in Table 2. The listed formats are not exhaustive.

Table 2: Data formats used in CODECO.

Type	Recommended formats
Project management and coordination data	Based on the project templates: Word, docx, Excel, xlsx, ppt, open document odt.
Experimental data	Sensor descriptions: WoT TD; YAML; YANG
Derived data	Latex for scientific publications; word for communication
Source code	Markdown for code documentation
Outputs derived from AB meetings	Based on the project templates: Word, docx, Excel, xlsx, ppt, open document odt
Outputs from IRCEP	Based on the project templates: Word, docx, Excel, xlsx, ppt, open document odt; xml

2.4 Template for Collecting Datasets

A template for collecting and specifying the datasets to be managed in the project is included in Appendix 1 and has also been uploaded to the CODECO repository being available to Partners under **02-WorkPackages/WP2-Use-Cases-OS_Ecosystem-ArchitecturalDesign/T2.1/DataCollection**. It prescribes collection of the following information:

- **Dataset name:** A descriptive name for the dataset.

⁷ <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project>

- **Dataset unique ID:** A unique identifier for the dataset based on some naming convention. To ensure uniqueness the id should be preceded with the prefix “HEU-101092696-CODECO”.
- **Dataset description:** A short but comprehensive description of the dataset.
- **Related WP/Task:** The WP(s)/task(s) of the CODECO workplan that include the work, which will produce/generate the dataset.
- **Data origin:** Information about the activity and actor that will produce the data.
- **Will you re-use any existing data? If YES, how?** The answer to this question indicates whether the dataset is produced based on existing datasets. It also explains the mechanisms (e.g., type of processing) that enables the production of the dataset.
- **Methodologies for data collection / generation:** It illustrate the methodologies of the data collection and production.
- **Data format:** The format of the dataset (e.g., CSV, JSON, PDF).
- **Data storage:** Information about where and how the dataset will be persisted and stored. This may include storage of the dataset in some open access repository like Zenodo.
- **Expected size of the data:** An indication of the order of magnitude of the volume of data in the dataset.
- **Metadata and standards:** A list of metadata formats and/or of related standards that are used in the representation of the dataset.
- **For whom might the dataset be useful?** An indication of the stakeholder groups that will benefit from access and use of the dataset.
- **Data access, sharing and licensing:** Information about the licenses of the dataset (e.g., Creative Commons – CC), as well as information about how to access and share the data (e.g., via some Application Programming Interface – API).

3 FAIR Data

3.1 Making Data Findable and Openly Accessible, Including Provisions for Metadata

CODECO addresses data following the FAIR methodology in its ecosystem, e.g., across the different use-cases and on the training tools. The specific data privacy and management aspects are therefore related with the policies at such end-user sites. To maximize the impact of CODECO research data, the results are shared within and beyond the consortium.

CODECO follows a FAIR and open data sharing policy. Selected data and results are, as soon as available, shared with the broad scientific community and the CODECO stakeholders via the CODECO Zenodo community, via the CODECO Eclipse Gitlab research project, and via activities (such as events) specifically targeting communication and dissemination.

All the CODECO assets are openly available to the industry and research communities, and to the CODECO stakeholders. CODECO assets that are software-based follow good practice for the development of OSS, guided by partner Eclipse in WP7.

Furthermore, the data being collected in use-cases will be also made publicly available via the CODECO Eclipse Gitlab.

Files will be deposited under closed, open, or embargoed access. In case some data has an embargo status, the date for the embargo will be provided and the repository will restrict

access to the data until the end of the embargo period; at which time, the content will become publicly available automatically.

Project outputs, including oral presentations, posters, and scientific publications (e.g., scientific papers, book chapters), will be shared also via the CODECO Zenodo community after an embargo period, if applicable.

The two main repositories mentioned, the CODECO Eclipse Gitlab and the CODECO Zenodo community, are already linked to the CODECO Website. Regular updates on new data are shared via the CODECO social channels, and specific posts target different CODECO stakeholders.

For each dataset stored in Eclipse, its metadata is recorded in a text file (e.g., a readme file) to serve as support for data interpretation and deposited together with the data to describe. As stated in the Grant Agreement of the CODECO project, metadata must be in a standard format and include the terms:

- “European Union (EU)” and “Horizon Europe”.
- the name of the action, acronym, and grant number.
- the publication date and length of embargo period if applicable.
- a persistent and unique identifier (such as Digital Object Identifiers (DOI)).

Note that the Zenodo platform facilitates the project to assign and management the persistent identifiers of its datasets, notably DOIs. The latter are a key prerequisite for ensuring a minimal level of fairness for the CODECO datasets.

3.2 Making Data Interoperable

To ensure interoperability, all datasets will use standardised formats, be accessible and easily shared; and the same applies to metadata. Open formats, such as YAML, are the preferred ones. As the project progresses and data is identified and collected, further information on making data interoperable will be outlined, namely, information on data and metadata vocabularies, standards, or methodology to follow to facilitate interoperability. Moreover, CODECO aligns with the Kubernetes recommendations (open documentation, open formats, and open-source code).

3.3 Increase Data Reuse

The CODECO open ecosystem is being built on an Open Science practice, where models for co-creation, specification and validation of the research are planned. Via the establishment of open use-cases, and via the offering of OSS stored on the CODECO Eclipse GitLab, CODECO has been providing open results to the community since an early stage (month six). All the CODECO assets are therefore openly available to the community: datasets, software, training, scientific publications. This shall increase impact and reusability of CODECO features.

The open datasets of the project will be licensed based on a Creative Commons (CC) license format. Business friendly licenses will be on the other hand used for the OSS results.

3.4 Dataset Handling

Following the initial 18 months of the project, datasets have been defined and a few started to be collected by project partners, pertaining to the use cases proposed by CODECO, providing detailed insights into their scope and application process, being available on the project's official repository. This data is not to be shared outside the consortium, as it not generated by CODECO research. If some of this data (augmented or modified/synthesized) does find a

purpose in the continuation of the development and it becomes part of a relevant dataset, then it will be anonymised following the rules laid out in this document.

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Responsible Entities

CODECO counts with a hierarchical Data management structure, where INO represents the **Project Data Manager** (Ana Solange Leal), assisting the Coordinator (FOR, Rute C. Sofia) in the overall data management.

All CODECO Partners are involved and are responsible, in one way or another, in data management (WP1, T1.1).

Under the guidance of INO, the CODECO partners play a major role ensuring that the data management provisions are applied.

4.2 Responsible Persons

Table 3 provides a summary concerning the data processes and responsible roles, and persons.

Table 3: Responsible Entities and Persons.

Description	Responsible	Partner and Person
Collection and curation of data in pilots	Pilot leaders	P1: UGOE, Xiaoming Fu P2: i2CAT, Jordi Marias Parella P3: TID, Luis Contreras P4: UPM, David Jimenez P5: FOR, Rute C. Sofia P6: ALM, Andries Stam
Processing and preservation of data across CODECO	WPL of WP1 and WP6	Rute Sofia (FOR), Ana Solange Leal (INO), Pedro Monteiro (INO), Xiaoming Fu (UGOE)
Responsible for publishing and sharing data	Pilot leaders, data owners	P1: UGOE, Xiaoming Fu P2: i2CAT, Rizkallah Touma P3: TID, Luis Contreras P4: UPM, David Jimenez P5: FOR, Rute C. Sofia P6: ALM, Andries Stam
DME creation and updates	Project Data Manager	Ana Solange Leal (INO) and Pedro Monteiro (INO)

4.3 Curation

The main aspects of curation are as follows:

- Data from **CODECO first level** (rf. section 2.2) will be organized and preserved by the CODECOs WP1 and WP6, depending on the type of data. Project management data will be processed internally and shall not be passed on to third parties outside of the project, except funding entities as may be required by any applicable reporting obligations. Deliverables, scientific publications, will be stored in the CODECO Zenodo and linked to the Website, as has been explained in Deliverable D1.

- Data resulting from the **CODECO second level** (rf. to section 2.2) will be preserved and stored via the CODECO Eclipse GitLab Research project⁸.
- Data resulting from the **CODECO third level** (rf. to section 2.2) will be processed and personally identifiable features (faces, license plates, etc) will be removed or obfuscated and stored in the open CODECO Eclipse GitLab.
- Data resulting from the **CODECO fourth level** will be organized and made available both via the CODECO Website and via the CODECO Zenodo Community

5 Data Preservation, Storage and Privacy

The following guidelines will be followed to ensure the security of the data:

- Store project related data in the CODECO internal repository (based on MS Teams).
- Encrypt data if it is deemed necessary by the participating researchers.
- Limit the use of USB flash drives.
- Label files in a systematically structured way to ensure the coherence of the final dataset.

5.1 Data Storage and Backup

All data detailed in section 2.1 will be stored and controlled by the CODECO Coordinator (FOR) and the INO team (CODECO management team). The CODECO internal MS teams repository is regularly backed up, and ZENODO has its own backup system.

Additionally, partners are recommended to store locally their necessary work data at all four levels described in section 2.2.

5.2 Data Selection and Preservation

The data produced at the CODECO second level relates with open-source code and is therefore a primary outcome of the project, and thus very important for the broader research community. The code, kept in the ECL CODECO GitLab, will be updated on a regular basis, with a software development standard of “*commit often and early*”. This will guarantee fully documented and reproducible source code and project results.

The CODECO third level of data will be stored at the CODECO ECL GitLab once it has been processed and ensured that it has been anonymized. This data is very important to be available for reuse in multiple domains and different applications, not yet foreseen by the project partners.

Scientific publications and corresponding datasets will be shared through ZENODO and other databases to promote the data making FAIR (see Section 3.1). The CODECO ZENODO management team (UGOE, INO and FOR) is responsible for the data curation and preservation.

5.3 Data Destruction

The different levels of data in CODECO are expected to live after the project lifetime. However, there may be cases where data expires, or one of the Partners (or external participants in the data collection) requests deletion of the data in accordance with Article 17 of GDPR, which concerns the Right to erasure. In this case, the data responsible entity (rf. to Table 3) will handle a secure deletion process, after consultation with the CODECO Project Data Manager (INO) and the CODECO Coordinator (FOR). For this process, CODECO shall consider secure data erasure methods (e.g., specific software), ensuring that the deleted data will not be

⁸ <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project>

recoverable after destruction. Moreover, CODECO shall create an auditable report for the process.

6 Ethical Aspects

Ethical aspects in CODECO are handled in WP1. The data that will be collected during the CODECO project is being handed in line with the highest ethical standards and the applicable European, international, and national law on ethical principles. The CODECO data is under no specific legal requirements and will be shared after an embargo period, if applicable. No dataset containing confidential information, or any ethical or legal issues, will be deposited.

CODECO relies on aspects that relate with AI (such as governance and resilience) and handles datasets, and therefore, ethical aspects may arise about data privacy, potential for infringement of human rights, personal data collection and misuse of technologies developed.

During the CODECO development, ethical and security aspects need to be monitored and assessed. CODECO contemplates different activities in WP1, WP5 and WP6, to handle the security, information sensitivity and ethical aspects regarding data collected, and research developed.

The overall process for Ethical and Security assessment is described in the CODECO handbook (D1) and revised each year. The CODECO Executive Board (EB), together with the CODECO internal Ethics Committee (ETC), follows the processes as proposed in DME (Deliverable D2/D3, WP1) and ensures that partners follow the proposed rules, making sure that they conform to the legislation regulations in force in the countries where the research will be carried out, as well as to the EC Ethical Legislation.

For AI, CODECO counts with a specific AI governance and resilience methodology that has derived specific checks to be done across CODECO use-cases and CODECO technological components, being developed in WP5 (Deliverable D15, M18, June 2024)

The ETC, represented in Table 4, is coordinated by partner INO (Ana Solange Leal) and handles the following aspects:

- Reviews datasets provided by partners, ensuring alignment with D2 and D3.
- Ensures that the GA aspects concerning Ethics are being adequately followed.

Table 4: The CODECO ETC members.

Name	Affiliation	Role in CODECO
Ana Solange Leal	INOVA	Data Manager/Data sources
Marco Jahn	ECL	Open-source ecosystem coordination
Luis Garces-Erice	IBM	Focus on data observability

The ETC shall meet regularly with the project management team and consortium, every quartal, aligned with the plenary meetings, to oversee the right approach to the handling of the project related data (WP1, T1.1). The ETC will follow the proposed DME (D2/D3) and ensure that partners follow the proposed rules, making sure that they conform to the legislation regulations in force in the countries where the research will be carried out, as well as to the EC Ethical Legislation.

6.1 Processes

The verification process is the responsibility of the entity owning the data, as has been detailed in Table 3 (rf. to section 4.1). The verification process is detailed in Table 5, involving six distinct steps. All these numbered steps need to be documented and confirmed by the persons involved in these steps. The feasibility and timeline of the steps should be gauged from a per-case perspective, as the process behind the collection of data can vary according to multiple variables.

Table 5 - Data Verification process

Step	Process	Responsible Entity
1	Identify the dataset that is relevant	Developer of the Partner working with the dataset
2	Verify if there is any PII present - for CODECO we adhere to directive 95/46/ECi1 which includes any information on the dataset or metadata that includes information capable of identifying a person via an ID number, or factors specific to physical, physiological, mental, economic, cultural, or social identity	
3	Removal of PII	
4	Request an additional verification of the data by a responsible from a different organization in the consortium	Developer of the organization working with the dataset contacts a second opinion to verify if all PII was removed from the dataset
5	The dataset is made available to the ETC for verification of compliance, and any other potential ethical issues and bias	ETC
6	The controller of the data for publishing (see section 2.2), verifies the compliance of the dataset as well with the set rules and then publishes it	Controller of data

6.2 GDPR Compliance

The consortium is committed to conducting the project in accordance with any applicable local laws that apply such as the General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 (GDPR) (collectively referred to as the EU Data Protection Legislation).

To ensure GDPR compliance, no data will be collected or used without the explicit informed consent of the subjects (e.g., users) concerned. In this direction, users/subjects provided data must sign a proper informed consent form. The form will make explicit who has access to the collected data, as well as for how long the data will be securely stored and subsequently deleted. Users/subjects will be also free to access their own data whenever they like. This will empower the Individuals involved to make a voluntary informed decision about whether to participate in CODECO processes based on knowledge of the scope, purpose, procedures, and outcomes of the project. Moreover, CODECO actors (e.g., end-users) will also have the possibility to gain access to additional information about their personal data and the way they are processed. Likewise, they will be able to revoke their consent at any time.

7 Other Issues

At this moment, no other national / funder / sectorial / departmental procedures for data management have been applied.

8 Use-Cases Considerations

The CODECO key technological blocks are being explored via the use of six use-cases (UC) which serve as basis for experimentation and demonstrations across three different European competitiveness markets: Smart Cities, Energy, Manufacturing. Each partner leading a UC is its own Data Manager. A specific team member of the partner oversees data gathering and quality management, aligned with WP1. Each UC leader will therefore execute its own data management on the specific UC. In this section, considerations concerning data aspects are done for each use-case.

8.1 Smart Cities

P1– Smart Monitoring of the Public Infrastructure – led by UGOE, will be employed to assist the smart monitoring of Göttingen’s public infrastructure by integrating CODECO in mobile Edge nodes across the city. It foresees two (2) datasets: *HEU-101092696-CODECO-infracraff*; and *HEU-101092696-CODECO-highpoint*, described in Annex II.

Similarly, **P2 - Vehicular Digital Twin for safe urban mobility** – led by I2CAT, demonstrates how the CODECO framework can support the deployment of vehicular digital twin services that enhance safety of Vulnerable Road Users (VRU) in urban environments. This UC foresees three (3) datasets: *HEU-101092696-CODECO-Trajectories*; *HEU-101092696-CODECO-Cyclist*; and *HEU-101092696-CODECO-VRUMobility*, , described in Annex III.

Both UCs have the potential to film people and vehicles, which might constitute a privacy violation when storing the collected and processed data. For this purpose, CODECO partners responsible for the UC will immediately blur faces of people and license plates of vehicles filmed at earliest Edge iteration as possible. Stored data will only contain this censored / anonymised data version.

Concerning **P3 – MDS across Decentralised Edge-Cloud** – led by TID, focus on the smart and efficient distribution of media content across a multi-domain, the CODECO project will also need to consider privacy concerning to data collection and strict data privacy policies and regulations, such as the GDPR in the European Union. This may include measures such as anonymizing user data and other Personally Identifiable Information (PII) present, obtaining user consent for data collection, and implementing robust data security measures to protect against unauthorized access and data breaches. This UC plans to use and made available two (2) datasets *HEU-101092696-CODECO-P3-MDS-MediaConsumptionTraffic* and *HEU-101092696-CODECO-P3-MDS-MediaConsumptionAccesses*, described in Annex IV.

8.2 Energy

P4 – Demand Side Management in Decentralised Grids – led by UPM, focuses on the deployment of Edge-based Smart Energy Nodes to provide a solution for energy controlling and adjusting in real time, people filmed / photographed will be immediately blurred with the same process. Stored data will only contain this censored / anonymized data version. The data is not expected to contain PII, but if it does contain it, it will also be removed.

The UC will handle energy datasets and if consumable energy datasets will be used, a consent form provided by CODECO shall be collected. Currently, the UC plans to use and made available four (4) datasets: *HEU-101092696-CODECO-EnergyConsumptionUPM-A*; *HEU-101092696-CODECO-EnergyConsumptionUPM-B*; *HEU-101092696-CODECO-EnergyConsumptionUPM-C*; and *HEU-101092696-CODECO-EnergyConsumptionUPM-D*, , described in Annex V.

P6 – Smart Buildings – led by ALM, will apply the CODECO technologies to their Crownstone smart buildings solution. Like happens in the other UCs, people who are filmed / photographed will be immediately blurred with the same process. Stored data will only contain this censored / anonymized data version. At this stage, the UC foresees one (1) dataset: *HEU-101092696-CODECO-AlmendeCrownstone*, , described in Annex VII.

8.3 Manufacturing

P5 – Wireless AGV control for flexible factories – led by FOR, focuses on the optimization of the overall efficiency of AGV. In case people are filmed / photographed, then it will be immediately blurred with the same process. Stored data will only contain this censored/anonymized data version. Data must be properly managed and stored to prevent data breaches or loss of sensitive information. Additional data that may be collected may relate with maps of obstacles for each AGV, or additional tasks passed to the AGVs.

Currently, this UC plans to use and made available two (2) datasets: *HEU-101092696-CODECO-UC5-AGVTasks* and *HEU-101092696-CODECO-UC5-AGVSensing*, , described in Annex VI.

9 Summary

This document is the second version of the DME which describes the main principles and guidelines for data management under the CODECO project. D3 include a concrete list of datasets that will be produced by project, including detailed information about each one of the datasets. As a living document, it will be updated throughout the project's lifetime. Further versions of the DME will include the eventually updating of the online research data repository where data are collected and shared, and the description of the dataset and research data gradually generated and collected.

Annex I – Dataset Information Collection Template

Dataset Information Template *(to be completed by each partner in charge of the dataset)*

Dataset name	
Dataset unique ID	
Dataset description	
Related WP/Task	
Data origin	
Will you re-use any existing data? If YES, how?	
Methodologies for data collection / generation	
Data format	
Data storage	
Expected size of the data	
Metadata and standards	<i>(e.g., Basic descriptive metadata (such as title, author, date created and keywords) will accompany the dataset)</i>
For whom might the dataset be useful?	
Data access, sharing and licensing	

Annex II – Dataset Information P1– Smart Monitoring of the Public Infrastructure

Dataset name	Infrared traffic scenario dataset
Dataset unique ID	HEU-101092696-CODECO-infratraff
Dataset description	This dataset will contain infrared images/videos of some traffic areas in different periods (day and night, different seasons). The data will be collected by thermal cameras in real traffic scenarios at the city periphery. Thermal cameras will be installed at 3-5 meters height at a depression angle. We may also add some labels to the data to better train our vehicle detection and counting function (number of vehicles).
Related WP/Task	WP5
Data origin	UGOE and municipalities
Will you re-use any existing data? If YES, how?	No
Methodologies for data collection / generation	Infrared images/videos are captured using thermal cameras placed at a height of 3-5 meters at a depression angle. The cameras are installed in traffic scenarios at the city periphery. Data is collected during different periods of the whole day and throughout the different seasons to capture a variety of traffic conditions. The images are processed, identifying, and counting the number of vehicles present in each image. The final dataset includes the raw infrared images/videos and their corresponding labels.
Data format	MPEG4/JPEG, XML
Data storage	The raw data will be uploaded to S3 data storage service provided by GWDG. The data will be utilized and processed based on this cloud-based storage platform. The final datasets will be updated to the CODECO Eclipse GitLab.
Expected size of the data	Hundreds of GB – dozens of TB
Metadata and standards	Author – UGOE Keywords: infrared traffic scenario
For whom might the dataset be useful?	UGOE
Data access, sharing and licensing	The dataset is hosted on CODECO Eclipse GitLab. Users can access the data through a web interface or by using our RESTful API for more advanced queries. Users are permitted to download and share the data for non-commercial purposes. Any publications or presentations based on these data should credit the source. The datasets will be licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 International License (CC BY-NC 4.0). The data may not be used for commercial purposes without explicit permission.

Dataset name	High-density urban scenario point cloud dataset
Dataset unique ID	HEU-101092696-CODECO-highpoint
Dataset description	This dataset will contain point clouds of some urban scenarios in different periods (day and night, different seasons). The data will be collected by LiDARs

	in real urban scenarios (crowded streets, city center). We may also add some labels to the data to better train our pedestrian detection and counting function (number of pedestrians).
Related WP/Task	WP5
Data origin	UGOE and municipalities
Will you re-use any existing data? If YES, how?	No
Methodologies for data collection / generation	Point clouds are captured using LiDAR scanners situated in urban scenarios. (crowded streets, city center) Data is collected during different periods of the whole day and throughout the different seasons to capture a variety of pedestrian behaviours and densities. The raw LiDAR data is processed to generate 3D point clouds of the scanned areas. The point clouds are then processed, identifying, and counting the number of pedestrians present in each frame. The final dataset includes the raw point cloud data and their corresponding labels.
Data format	High-density urban scenario point cloud dataset: LAS, XML
Data storage	The raw data will be uploaded to S3 data storage service provided by GWDG. The data will be utilized and processed based on this cloud-based storage platform. The final datasets will then be uploaded to the CODECO Eclipse GitLab.
Expected size of the data	Hundreds of GB – dozens of TB
Metadata and standards	Author – UGOE Keywords: high-density urban scenario
For whom might the dataset be useful?	UGOE
Data access, sharing and licensing	The dataset is hosted on CODECO Eclipse GitLab. Users can access the data through a web interface or by using our RESTful API for more advanced queries. Users are permitted to download and share the data for non-commercial purposes. Any publications or presentations based on these data should credit the source. The datasets will be licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 International License (CC BY-NC 4.0). The data may not be used for commercial purposes without explicit permission.

Annex III – Dataset Information P2 - Vehicular Digital Twin for Safe Urban Mobility

Dataset name	Private Vehicle Trajectory on an urban environment with collisions
Dataset unique ID	HEU-101092696-CODECO-Trajectories
Dataset description	Datasets generated with SUMO simulator to recreate a reckless driving experience. The objective of this scenario is to increase the possibility of both lateral and frontal collisions between vehicles. There are two different scenarios situated in the center of Barcelona, which are geo-localized, so it can be extracted the real coordinates of the vehicles in those scenarios.
Related WP/Task	WP2
Data origin	The data has been produced with the SUMO Traffic simulator.
Will you re-use any existing data? If YES, how?	It is not based on any other existing datasets.
Methodologies for data collection / generation	To generate these datasets there are made several modifications to the SUMO simulator (done with the TraCI interface) which adds more reckless vehicles that will ignore the traffic lights and sometimes circulate at higher velocities than permitted. Then the same TraCI interface is used to extract the data from the simulation (both the recording of the collisions, and the positions of all the vehicles).
Data format	The record of the collisions is stored in a XML file with the same format extracted from TraCI, and the positions are stored as a CSV file.
Data storage	The dataset is published and shared in a public GitHub repository: https://github.com/Fundacio-i2CAT/Collisions_Datasets and is available as well in the CODECO Eclipse GitLab.
Expected size of the data	There are several types of datasets, the shorter ones cover between 5 and 10 hours and are about 500-1000 MB. And the longer ones (like barcelona_v2.tar.xz), have a higher density of vehicles, and cover around 50 hours with 20 GB.
Metadata and standards	<i>To be decided in the future</i>
For whom might the dataset be useful?	The dataset is mainly created to train ML algorithms which can predict and avoid collisions between vehicles in a realistic urban scenario. So, a possible stakeholder would be any research groups related to autonomous or connected vehicles or generating ML algorithms.
Data access, sharing and licensing	ODC Open Database License (ODbL)

Dataset name	Cyclist Dataset for Object Detection in YOLO Format
Dataset unique ID	HEU-101092696-CODECO-Cyclist
Dataset description	This dataset contains 13.7k labelled images, 1000 of which don't contain cyclists. The size of each image is 2048x1024 and the bounding box follows YOLO's format: [id, center_x, center_y, width, height]. The dataset has a size of 2 GB.

	<p>The dataset has been created by X. Li, F. Flohr, Y. Yang, H. Xiong, M. Braun, S. Pan, K. Li, and D. M. Gavrilu and has been titled “Tsinghua-Daimler Cyclist Detection Benchmark Dataset in Yolo format for Object Detection”.</p> <p>The dataset is freely available for non-commercial purposes such as academic research, teaching, scientific publications, or personal experimentation. License: <i>Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 3.0 IGO (CC BY-NC-SA 3.0 IGO)</i>.</p>
Related WP/Task	WP2
Data origin	<p>The data comes from a paper titled: A New Benchmark for Vision-Based Cyclist Detection and is posted on the Kaggle website (Cyclist Dataset for Object Detection Kaggle).</p> <p>X. Li, F. Flohr, Y. Yang, H. Xiong, M. Braun, S. Pan, K. Li, and D. M. Gavrilu. A New Benchmark for Vision-Based Cyclist Detection. In Proc. of the IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium (IV), Gothenburg, Sweden, pp.1028-1033, 2016.</p> <p>The dataset also has an affiliation with Daimler.</p>
Will you re-use any existing data? If YES, how?	N/A. The dataset will be used as is.
Methodologies for data collection / generation	N/A. The dataset will be used as is, no modification or addition will be done.
Data format	The dataset consists of two folders, the first one has images in jpeg format and the second folder has the labels for each image, in txt files in the YOLO format.
Data storage	The dataset is posted on Kaggle: Cyclist Dataset for Object Detection Kaggle
Expected size of the data	2 GB
Metadata and standards	<p>Tsinghua-Daimler Cyclist Detection Benchmark Dataset in yolo format for Object detection.</p> <p>The creators of the dataset are X. Li, F. Flohr, Y. Yang, H. Xiong, M. Braun, S. Pan, K. Li, and D. M. Gavrilu. Also, all rights not expressly granted are reserved by Daimler.</p> <p>The dataset follows the YOLO format.</p>
For whom might the dataset be useful?	For computer vision experts that want to train a YOLO model to detect cyclists as a single entity. Unit now cyclists were detected as a combination of bicycle+person.
Data access, sharing and licensing	<u>Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 3.0 IGO (CC BY-NC-SA 3.0 IGO)</u>

Dataset name	Urban environment mobility patterns with VRUs
Dataset unique ID	HEU-101092696-CODECO-VRUMobility
Dataset description	In the UC2 scenario, comprehensive data regarding the trajectories and positions of various road users (such as pedestrians, bikes, and electric scooters) as well as cars will be meticulously collected over a specific time. Each user's data will be tagged anonymously, ensuring privacy and security. The collected data will encompass essential trajectory fields typically

	<p>transmitted through a V2X VAM or CAM message, including latitude, longitude, heading, speed, acceleration, and margins of certainty. Additionally, numerous other relevant data points will be recorded.</p> <p>This valuable dataset will serve a twofold purpose. Firstly, it will be utilized to enhance the accuracy and effectiveness of the risk detector by leveraging real-world data from the specific scenario in which the detector is being tested. Secondly, the stored data can be harnessed for other purposes, particularly to enhance various aspects related to the CODECO framework. For instance, it can aid in refining orchestration processes by improving the estimation of users present in a particular area. Furthermore, the data can contribute to optimizing service metrics by facilitating better anticipation of user behavior in situations that necessitate service improvement.</p>
Related WP/Task	WP5
Data origin	Data collected through camera sensors and V2X communications
Will you re-use any existing data? If YES, how?	No
Methodologies for data collection / generation	During a few days, the data of the VRUs and cars in the UC2 scenario will be collected.
Data format	The data will be stored firstly in a database and then dumped into CSV
Data storage	The dataset will be made available in the CODECO Eclipse GitLab.
Expected size of the data	~10GB
Metadata and standards	VRUs, cars, urban mobility, UPC campus, I2CAT offices,
For whom might the dataset be useful?	There will be the option to spot and improve the risky detection algorithms in real situations.
Data access, sharing and licensing	The license has yet to be decided and the anonymized and RGPD-compliant way of storing this data as well.

Annex IV – Dataset Information P3 – MDS across Decentralised Edge-Cloud

Dataset name	P3 MDS Media Consumption Traffic
Dataset unique ID	HEU-101092696-CODECO-P3-MDS-MediaConsumptionTraffic
Dataset description	This data set refers to a standard media consumption traffic behavior. The main goal to this data set is to simulate how actions of the CODECO users' clients will affect to the network behavior and, therefore, how our system should take actions to respond and anticipate these usage patterns.
Related WP/Task	WP5, T5.1 and T5.3
Data origin	This data will be generated in two different ways: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Network behavior will be simulated with Data Injectors as Ixia breaking Point or EveNG traffic simulation tool. 2. Users' behavior will be simulated with automated scripts being connected to MEC APIs. <p>These two types of data will be integrated in a way that the points with more users and requests should be the ones with more network traffic and vice-versa.</p>
Will you re-use any existing data? If YES, how?	The main intention is to generate specific synthetic data sets for these tests. There is not initial intention to re-use the data sets.
Methodologies for data collection / generation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Definition of different traffic behaviours to be studied. - Use of commercial data generators available for this use case. - We will not use real data or personal data at all.
Data format	To be studied. The initial intention is using pcaps.
Data storage	The dataset will be available in CODECO's official repositories.
Expected size of the data	Orders of GB.
Metadata and standards	To be studied.
For whom might the dataset be useful?	AI engines to train and improve their decisions for Network resources allocation.
Data access, sharing and licensing	The dataset will become freely / openly accessible based on an open license.

Dataset name	P3 MDS Media Consumption Accesses
Dataset unique ID	HEU-101092696-CODECO-P3-MDS-MediaConsumptionAccesses
Dataset description	This dataset refers to standard media access behavior. The main purpose of this dataset is to simulate how MDS clients access their resources and how it affects the behavior of the network, and therefore how our system should take actions to respond and anticipate these usage patterns.
Related WP/Task	WP5, T5.1 and T5.3
Data origin	This data will be the users' behavior to be simulated with automated scripts being connected to MEC APIs.

Will you re-use any existing data? If YES, how?	The main intention is to generate specific synthetic data sets for these tests. There is not an initial intention to re-use the data sets.
Methodologies for data collection / generation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Definition of different traffic behaviours to be studied. - Use of python-based scripts to automatize the connection to APIs. - We will not use real data or personal data at all.
Data format	To be studied. The initial intention is using TXT/JSON.
Data storage	The dataset will be available in CODECO's official repositories.
Expected size of the data	Orders of KB.
Metadata and standards	To be studied.
For whom might the dataset be useful?	AI engines to train and improve their decisions for Network resources allocation.
Data access, sharing and licensing	The dataset will become freely / openly accessible based on an open license.

Annex V – Dataset Information P4 – Demand Side Management in Decentralised Grids

Dataset name	Energy Consumption in the Telecommunication School of UPM – Building A			
Dataset unique ID	HEU-101092696-CODECO-EnergyConsumptionUPM-A			
Dataset description	<p>The Escuela Técnica Superior de Ingenieros de Telecomunicación (ETSIT) at Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM), is an Engineering School made up of four different buildings connected to the grid. All buildings have been monitored, in terms of consumption, with a different discretization degree. Moreover, every building has its own particularities within the academic ecosystem and some of them have their own generation.</p> <p>This time-series provides information about the Building A of the ETSIT-UPM, the first one built in 1965. The building shares with Building D a medium (17.5 kV) to low tension (420V) transformer of 630 kVA. Building A was designed with a maximum power consumption of 862kW (1,250A), although consumptions greater than 500kW have never been registered.</p> <p>Building A is devoted to academic activities, where a cafeteria, library, classes, and professors' offices are included. Monitoring consumption has been divided in 5 measurements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - L1: General line (1,250A line with a 1000:5 current transformer) that monitors all Building A consumption. - L2: HVAC (400A line with a 400:5 current transformer) that monitors air conditioner lines of Building A. Heat is handled by gas installations that are not monitored. - L3: Cafeteria (400A line with a 200:5 current transformer) that monitors cafeteria consumption. - L4: Library (100A line with 100:5 current transformer) that monitors library consumption. - L5: Library HVAC (160A line with 150:5 current transformer) that monitors air conditioner lines of the library. Heat is handled by gas installations that are not monitored. 			
Related WP/Task	T 5.3			
Data origin	Data is acquired by UPM on its premises. Building A has been monitored through 5 measurements.			
Will you re-use any existing data? If YES, how?	Not yet defined.			
Methodologies for data collection / generation	Data is acquired through several voltage and current sensors. Stored in a CSV file			
Data format	CSV			
Data storage	CODECO Eclipse GitLab			
Expected size of the data	59MB Two years (Time Horizon) – 1 min (Data Resolution)			
Metadata and standards	<i>Column</i>	<i>Header</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Format</i>
	1	#Timestamp	seconds from 01/01/1970 (UTC+01:00)	integer number
	2	date	day, month, and year of the data	DD/MM/YYYY

	3	<i>time</i>	<i>hour, minute, and seconds of the data in 24-hour time format</i>	<i>HH:MM: SS</i>
	4	<i>L1</i>	<i>Total power consumption of Building A [W]</i>	<i>integer number</i>
	5	<i>L2</i>	<i>HVAC power consumption of Building A [W]</i>	<i>integer number</i>
	6	<i>L3</i>	<i>Cafeteria power consumption [W]</i>	<i>integer number</i>
	7	<i>L4</i>	<i>Library power consumption [W]</i>	<i>integer number</i>
	8	<i>L5</i>	<i>HVAC library power consumption [W]</i>	<i>integer number</i>
For whom might the dataset be useful?	Researchers looking for consumption datasets to analyse.			
Data access, sharing and licensing	Open Access Download			

Dataset name	Energy Consumption in the Telecommunication School of UPM –Building B
Dataset unique ID	HEU-101092696-CODECO-EnergyConsumptionUPM-B
Dataset description	<p>The Escuela Técnica Superior de Ingenieros de Telecomunicación (ETSIT) at Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM), is an Engineering School made up of four different buildings connected to the grid. All buildings have been monitored, in terms of consumption, with a different discretization degree. Moreover, every building has its own particularities within the academic ecosystem and some of them have their own generation.</p> <p>This time-series provides information about the Building B of the ETSIT-UPM, the second one built in 1975. The building shares with Building C two mid (17500 V) to low (420V) tension transformers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One oil-filled electric transformer of 630 kVA. • One dry-type electrical transformer of 1 MVA. <p>Building B was designed with a maximum power consumption of 552kW (800A).</p> <p>Building B is devoted to academic and research activities, where students' classes and professors' offices are included. Monitoring consumption has been divided in 2 measurements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - L1: General line (800A line with an 800:5 current transformer) that monitors all Building B consumption. - L2: HVAC (250A line with a 250:5 current transformer) that monitors air conditioner lines of Building B. Heat is handled by gas installations that are not monitored.
Related WP/Task	T5.3
Data origin	Data is acquired by UPM on its premises. Building A has been monitored through 2 measurements.
Will you re-use any existing data? If YES, how?	

Methodologies for data collection / generation	Data is acquired through several power, voltage, and current sensors. Stored in a CSV file.			
Data format	CSV			
Data storage	CODECO Eclipse GitLab			
Expected size of the data	52 MB – 2 years (Time Horizon) - 1 minute (Time Resolution)			
Metadata and standards	<i>Column</i>	<i>Header</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Format</i>
	1	#Timestamp	Seconds from 01/01/1970 (CET-1)	Integer number
	2	Date	Day, Month and Year of the data	DD/MM/YYYY
	3	Time	Hour, Minute and Seconds of the data in 24-hour time format	HH:MM:SS
	4	L1	Total power consumption of Building B [W]	integer number
	5	L2	HVAC power consumption of Building B [W]	integer number
For whom might the dataset be useful?	Researchers looking for consumption datasets to analyse.			
Data access, sharing and licensing	Open Access Download			

Dataset name	Energy Consumption in the Telecommunication School of UPM – Building C
Dataset unique ID	HEU-101092696-CODECO-EnergyConsumptionUPM-C
Dataset description	<p>The Escuela Técnica Superior de Ingenieros de Telecomunicación (ETSIT) at Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM), is an Engineering School made up of four different buildings connected to the grid. All buildings have been monitored, in terms of consumption, with a different discretization degree. Moreover, every building has its own particularities within the academic ecosystem and some of them have their own generation.</p> <p>These time-series provides information about the Building C of the ETSIT-UPM, the third one built in 1985. The building shares with Building C two mid (17.5 kV) to low (420V) tension transformers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One oil-filled electric transformer of 630 kVA. • One dry-type electrical transformer of 1000 kVA. <p>Building C was designed with a maximum power consumption of 1.104kW (1600A).</p> <p>Building C is devoted to research activities, where 2 research institutes and professors' offices are included. Monitoring consumption has been divided in 2 measurements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - L1: HVAC (630A line with a 400:5 current transformer) that monitors air conditioner lines of Building C. Heat is handled by gas installations that are not monitored. - L5: Ground floor (100A with a 50:5 current transformer) that monitors all consumptions of ground floor. It basically includes interior lighting, an assembly hall and a couple of conference meetings.

	<p>- L6: First floor east (250A with a 100:5 current transformer) that monitors the east side of the first floor with professors' offices and some small electronic labs.</p> <p>- L7: First floor west (250A with a 100:5 current transformer) that monitors the west side of the first floor with professors' offices and some small electronic labs.</p> <p>- L8: Second floor east (250A with a 100:5 current transformer) that monitors the east side of the second floor with professors' offices and some small electronic labs.</p> <p>- L9: Second floor west (250A with a 100:5 current transformer) that monitors the west side of second first floor with professors' offices and some small electronic labs.</p> <p>- L10: Third floor east (250A with a 100:5 current transformer) that monitors the east side of the third floor with professors' offices and some small electronic labs.</p> <p>- L11: Third floor west (250A with a 100:5 current transformer) that monitors the west side of the third floor with professors' offices and some small electronic labs.</p> <p>- L12: Outdoor lighting (100A with a 50:5 current transformer) that monitors the outdoor lighting.</p> <p>- L_Tot: General line (1600A line with a 1000:5 current transformer) that monitors all Building C consumption.</p> <p>- L13: Institute for Optoelectronic Systems and Microtechnology (630A line with a 600:5 current transformer) that monitors the complete consumption of a research institute.</p>			
Related WP/Task	WP5 - T5.3			
Data origin	Data is acquired by UPM in its premises. Building C has been monitored through 11 measurements.			
Will you re-use any existing data? If YES, how?	To be defined.			
Methodologies for data collection / generation	Data is acquired through several voltage and current sensors. Stored in a CSV file			
Data format	CSV			
Data storage	CODECO Eclipse GitLab			
Expected size of the data	128MB Two years (Time Horizon) – 1 min (Data Resolution)			
Metadata and standards	<i>Column</i>	<i>Header</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Format</i>
	1	#Timestamp	seconds from 01/01/1970 (UTC+01:00)	integer number
	2	Date	day, month, and year of the data	DD/MM/YYYY
	3	Time	hour, minute, and seconds of the data in 24-hour time format	HH:MM:SS
	4	L1	HVAC power consumption of Building C [W]	float number

	5	L5	Ground floor power consumption of Building C [W]	float number
	6	L6	1st floor power (east) consumption of Building C [W]	float number.
	7	L7	1st floor power (west) consumption of Building C [W]	float number.
	8	L8	2nd floor power (east) consumption of Building C [W]	float number.
	9	L9	2nd floor power (west) consumption of Building C [W]	float number
	10	L10	3rd floor power (east) consumption of Building C [W]	float number
	11	L11	3rd floor power (west) consumption of Building C [W]	float number
	12	L12	Outdoor lighting consumption of Building C [W]	float number
	13	L1_Tot	Total consumption of Building C [W]	float number
	14	L13	Institute for Optoelectronic Systems and Microtechnology (ISOM) consumption [W]	float number
For whom might the dataset be useful?	Researchers looking for consumption datasets to analyse.			
Data access, sharing and licensing	Open Access Download			

Dataset name	Energy Consumption in the Telecommunication School of UPM – Building D
Dataset unique ID	HEU-101092696-CODECO-EnergyConsumptionUPM-D
Dataset description	<p>The Escuela Técnica Superior de Ingenieros de Telecomunicación (ETSIT) at Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM), is an Engineering School made up of four different buildings connected to the grid. All buildings have been monitored, in terms of consumption, with a different discretization degree. Moreover, every building has its own particularities within the academic ecosystem and some of them have their own generation.</p> <p>These time-series provides information about the Building D of the ETSIT-UPM, the last one built in 2004. The building shares with Building A a medium (17.5 kV) to low tension (420V) transformer of 630 kVA. Building D was designed with a maximum power consumption of 434 kW (630A), although consumptions greater than 100kW have never been registered.</p> <p>Building D is devoted to research, where we find several administrative offices, data computing workstations and electronics laboratories. All consumption lines are grouped in one single measurement. Hence, data provided in the time-series are monitored by means of a 3-phase meter with a current transformer of 300:5.</p>

Related WP/Task	T5.3			
Data origin	Data is acquired by UPM in its premises. Building D has been monitored through 1 measurement.			
Will you re-use any existing data? If YES, how?	To be defined			
Methodologies for data collection / generation	Data is acquired through several, power, voltage, and current sensors. Stored in a CSV file.			
Data format	CSV			
Data storage	CODECO Eclipse GitLab			
Expected size of the data	44 MB – 2 years (Time Horizon) - 1 minute (Time Resolution)			
Metadata and standards	<i>Column</i>	<i>Header</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Format</i>
	1	#Timestamp	Seconds from 01/01/1970 (CET-1)	Integer number
	2	Date	Day, Month and Year of the data	DD/MM/YYYY
	3	Time	Hour, Minute and Seconds of the data in 24-hour time format	HH:MM:SS
	4	Power	Total power consumption of Building DB[W]	integer number
For whom might the dataset be useful?	Researchers looking for consumption datasets to analyse.			
Data access, sharing and licensing	Open Access Download			

Annex VI – Dataset Information P5 – Wireless AGV control for flexible factories

Dataset name	UC5 AGV fleet tasks
Dataset unique ID	HEU-101092696-CODECO-UC5-AGVTasks
Dataset description	The dataset comprises different lists of tasks to be carried out by an AGV. A task is a tuple with at least the following fields: <id, source, destination, size (Mb), target location, action >. Different datasets shall be generated (synthetic data) for the purpose of validation.
Related WP/Task	WP5, T5.1-T5.3
Data origin	Task handler component in UC5, AGV controller. This will be a python-based service, which will generate synthetic data sets based on specific requirements.
Will you re-use any existing data? If YES, how?	The dataset shall be used within CODECO, and re-used by FOR in the context of its fortiss IIoT Lab.
Methodologies for data collection / generation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Python based service, capable of generating realistic tasks. - Volume of tasks to be varied. - Configuration of tasks to be varied. - Reference: VDMA AGV communication standards and guidelines.
Data format	Txt
Data storage	The dataset will be made available via the CODECO via the Eclipse CODECO GitLab
Expected size of the data	Orders of MB.
Metadata and standards	The task datasets shall include at least: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Header: title, author, affiliation, other relevant sources, creation date and purpose; license; expected update frequency • Body: 1 task (tuple) per line, where tuple fields are separated via a regular separator such as ““or “,”
For whom might the dataset be useful?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ICT, AR, SMEs
Data access, sharing and licensing	The dataset will become freely / openly accessible based on an open license (e.g., Creative Commons), expected by M20.

Dataset name	UC5 AGV Sensed data
Dataset unique ID	HEU-101092696-CODECO-UC5-AGVSensing
Dataset description	Datasets in this category shall collect sensed information that may assist AGVs in an understanding of their surroundings, and in collision avoidance.
Related WP/Task	WP5, T5.1-T5.3

Data origin	Sensors and camera integrated into each AGV in UC5
Will you re-use any existing data? If YES, how?	The dataset shall be used within CODECO, and re-used by FOR in the context of its fortiss IIoT Lab.
Methodologies for data collection / generation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reference: VDMA AGV communication standards and guidelines. - Data to be collected over the course of several days (at least 2), different times of the day to reach a reasonable volume (e.g., 1-5 GB per AGV) and considering different signal conditions, as well as nLoS and LoS scenarios. - Data will be collected in each AGV, and first locally stored (FOR server). Data will be pre-processed to handle identifier and field obfuscation (e.g., IP, MAC) for the identified fields. - Similar larger datasets will also be searched (e.g., Kaggle).
Data format	<i>Txt, image, xls</i>
Data storage	The dataset will be made available via CODECO Eclipse CODECO in M20 (August 2024).
Expected size of the data	Orders of GB.
Metadata and standards	<p>Datasets in this category shall be developed per type of sensed data, e.g., routes, obstacles (video); environmental data (telemetry); etc.</p> <p>The task datasets shall include at least:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Header: title, author, affiliation, other relevant sources, creation date and purpose; license; expected update frequency • Body: id, timestamp, source id, storage id
For whom might the dataset be useful?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ICT - AR - SMEs
Data access, sharing and licensing	The dataset will become freely / openly accessible based on an open license (e.g., Creative Commons).

Annex VII – Dataset Information P6 – Smart Buildings

Dataset name	<i>AlmendeCrownstone Presence data</i>
Dataset unique ID	HEU-101092696-CODECO-AlmendeCrownstone
Dataset description	A test setup comprising 15 Crownstone are combined in a sphere (collection) and the RX/TX data recorded by each participating radio together with the timestamp is registered on average every second. It is possible to tag this data with additional measured values through added sensors using the microapp infrastructure such as e.g., humidity.
Related WP/Task	The WP(s)/task(s) of the CODECO workplan that include the work, which will produce/generate the dataset.
Data origin	The data is collected with a special USB Crownstone running the BTLE Mesh protocol to participate in the sphere's communication. The USB serial connection is then used to communicate the information to a local hub. The information is subsequently uploaded to a local influx database server.
Will you re-use any existing data? If YES, how?	No
Methodologies for data collection / generation	See above
Data format	CSV and JSON
Data storage	The data will be made available via the CODECO Eclipse GitLab (public version).
Expected size of the data	To volition. We use time periods as an indication, e.g. a week, a month.
Metadata and standards	No standards are applicable yet.
For whom might the dataset be useful?	Any future microapp developer, but as indicated, the data is GPR sensitive.
Data access, sharing and licensing	Non-public, potentially public in a (yet unknown) aggregated and/or anonymized form.